

The Use of Voice Recorder Application to Improve Students' Speaking Skill

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ABSTRAK

Bahasa Inggris adalah bahasa internasional, banyak buku sains dan pasar bisnis ekonomi di dunia ini menggunakan bahasa Inggris sebagai bahasa formal untuk saling terhubung. Namun pada kenyataannya, mempelajari bahasa Inggris sebagai bahasa kedua masih menjadi masalah bagi siswa Indonesia. Hal ini mungkin disebabkan oleh kurangnya kreativitas antara guru dan siswa dalam memanfaatkan hal-hal baru di sekitar kita setiap hari. Masalah siswa sangat beragam, mulai dari bentuk; kurangnya media, kurangnya rasa percaya diri, dan masih banyak lagi. Pada dasarnya, ada empat keterampilan yang dibutuhkan dalam program pembelajaran bahasa Inggris. Mereka adalah membaca, berbicara, mendengarkan, dan menulis. Berdasarkan keterampilan tersebut, berbicara adalah salah satu keterampilan terpenting dalam pembelajaran bahasa. Dengan berbicara, kita dapat menyampaikan informasi dan ide, dan memelihara hubungan sosial dengan berkomunikasi dengan orang lain. Dengan berbicara, orang-orang berinteraksi antara individu dan masyarakat. Penulis mencoba menggunakan aplikasi perekam suara sebagai media untuk meningkatkan keterampilan berbicara siswa dan menggunakan gambar sebagai media untuk mengontrol fokus siswa selama spek mereka, alasannya adalah karena setiap siswa di Indonesia khususnya di Jawa Barat memiliki telepon seluler. Telepon

seluler mereka sangat beragam dengan sistem operasi (OS) yang terkenal di telepon mereka, yaitu; iPhone, Android, BlackBerry, Microsoft. Perekam suara adalah fitur umum di setiap ponsel dan beragam model suara.

ABSTRACT

English is an international language, many science books and economic business market in this world use English as formal language to connect each other. But in fact, learning English as second language still became a problem for Indonesian students. It is might lack of creativity between teacher and learner in exploit new things around us every day. The students problem are so variety, start form; lack of media, lack of self confidence and many more. Basically, there are four skills required in English teaching learning program. They are reading, speaking, listening and writing. Base on those skill, speaking is one of the most important skill in language learning. By speaking, we can convey information and ideas, and maintain social relationship by communicating with others. By speaking people make interaction between individual and community. The writer tried to use voice recorder application as media to improve student in speaking skill and used picture as media to control student focus during their speak, the reason is because every students in Indonesia especially in west Java have phone cell. their phone cell are so variety with the famous operational system (OS) in their phone, they are; iPhone, Android, Blackberry, Microsoft. Voice recorder are common feature in every single phone and many variety of voice model.

INTRODUCTION

Learning language is a process, which need a method, media and technique. In specific discussion, there are some approach, method, technique and media used by the teacher to teach speaking. Comic become famous in recent time. Both children and adult people love comic. Based on Wright (2001), Modern comic book come intuitively by two workers in Eastern Colour Printing Company which collect several famous comic strip from news paper and put in order to magazine Since 1933, where two workers produce first modern comic, comic became very popular. Another subject is about speaking, speaking is one of the four skills that must be learned and mastered by the learners, especially Indonesian learners as non native speakers; by speaking we can convey global information, join with people in around of the world. this study use of comic figure to develop students speaking, because there is joy media to help students to express their idea by speak in English.

THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

Comic figure

As cited by Neil William and friends in Faculty of American Language Institute of New York University (1995). They have used Calvin and Hobbes as media to teach students in this university. In the world war II comic figure used as propaganda tool between America and Germany as showed by Disney Company. The comic figures not yet used by the teacher in this school. Nonetheless comic figures love by every people, hundred people else believe that comic figures is not good for child. Most of these comic figures also tell about negative thing which made parent worry if their children will imitate. Robert Thorndike working with DC Comics and Harold Downes create exercise language book by using pictures. It means that since the past, comic has to be strategies media in guide students to learn and contribute in world education. Base on those comic existence of comic figure ,the paper will be combine to develop simple sentence.

There many kinds of comic figures could be used in teaching and learning of speaking in the class room. The kinds of comic figures examples are; Naruto, Tin-Tin, and Spider man, Superman, X-Man, Dragon ball and many more. Those figures are very famous in world comic. The writer tried to use comic figure as media to develop student in speaking skill, the reason is because every comic figures have strange character, identity, and habitually who inspirited and influence many students. Comic figures are fun media to make students interest in learning English especially in speaking subject. Comic figure may usual media, but comic figure made is because the developer has massage whom want to tells to everyone.

Speaking

Speaking is an interactive process of constructing meaning that involves producing and receiving and processing information (Brown, 1994; Burns & Joyce, 1997). Its form and meaning are dependent on the context in which it occurs, including the participants themselves, their collective experiences, the physical environment, and the purposes for speaking. Speaking is communication tool, produced by human life to communicate each other. The term speaking can be defined as the people way to convey the message to people. It means speaking subject is need interaction between individual and other people. According to Harmer (2004:343) there three kinds of speaking situations in which we find ourselves, they are:

1. Interactive
2. Partially interactive; and (3) Non-interactive.

Interactive speaking include face-to-face conversations and telephone calls, in which we are alternately listening and speaking, and in which we have a chance to ask repetition, clarification, or slower speech from our conversation partner. Some speaking situations are partially interactive, such as giving a speech to on air audience, where the conversation is that the audience does not interrupt the speech. The speaker nevertheless can see the audience and judge from the expression on their face and body language whether or not he or she is being understood. Some few speaking situation maybe totally non- interactive, such as when recording speech for news broadcast or radio broadcast. Base on those explanations it can be concluded that speaking is a communication or sharing our ideas, message, opinion and argumentation, wants desire trough the language.

According to the Brooks (1964) in Tarigan (1981) Speaking is direct communicative activity or "face to face communication" while trough the discovery of enormous technologies like; Phone cell, TV, Internet. The writer believes that speaking not always as face to face communication anymore. Nowadays, people speak or talk using various tools of gadget without consider time, distance and place. Like example; Voice Recorder, Kakao Talk, We chat, Skype, Blackberry messenger, B-talk, anygram, Facebook any many more. Speaking is part of human socialization both one individual and community or person and group which have to action each other and give the influence. Based those definition means some interaction activity between human activity, speaking as a human tool to communicate with their community in daily life.

Voice Recorder Application toward speaking

Recording can be defined in many ways. One sense of the terms is notifying or documenting some notes or statements". Recording sounds using mechanical or electronic methods is quite different from notifying data or information. Recording method varies from visual to audible. There is a diverse range of recording medium including scripting, photographing, and drawing etc. Sound recording implies to preserve for listening again in future. However, recording sound differs from preserving an object visually. In that sense, recording sound can be defined as a progression of codifying or storage of human speech or singing, sound pertaining to instrumental music or sound effects using electronic or mechanical methods. This can be understood as a result of the scientific revolution.

Base on Morton (1924:57) There are four kinds of sound recording technologies that have emerged so far since the evolution of sound recording. Similarly, as far as the methods and procedures are

concerned four kinds of recording eras can be identified as Mechanical era, Electronic era, Magnetic era and Digital era that have continued from the early times to modern periods. They are:

- (1) Mechanical or acoustic recording
- (2) Electronic recording.
- (3) Magnetic recording
- (4) Digital recording

May Voice Recorder application are usual media in a phone cell, and simple. in few people, voice recorder application use to record conversation. Examples; Pers. journalism, broadcaster, and Vlogger. Voice recorder application is near media with daily live of students, because every students have phone cell to communicate with their family and friend and also to access the internet. By using voice recorder application students can learn with fun, student also more interest to express their feeling and mind. The student will tell and describe what they want using voice recorder application in their phone cell application. here are the simple steps in class room;

- 1. Teacher allowed the students to search picture or any medias.
- 2. Every individual carry their phone cell and open voice recorder application. The teacher gave a picture to help students inspiration, the pictures in this research are comic figures. Language focus in this research is simple present tense, and students chose picture (comic figures) and gave time to the students before they start to express their speak using voice recorder

DATA COLLECTION

Data Analysis Technique

a). Analysis data of students' speaking score, to analyses data from students' speaking score the writer used brown (2001:406-407), an oral proficiency test scoring categories as the standard of scoring students categories to describe students speaking score and progress in every cycle.

sample

In this case population decided by the teacher to get conclusion. The population is the second grade students of SMP N 1 Sindang.

INSTRUMENT

Research instrument used to measure, record and collect empirical data. It has to design as well as possible to produce accurate data. The research instruments are following:

- a. Spoken Test. Spoken test used by the writer to measure student's speaking progress and improvement in English speaking using picture. The test that used in individual performance in front of the class. It will conduct in whole process involving: a. record the speaking progress, at the end of the instructional as the post test result.
- b. Voice Recorder Application. Voice recorder application chose as the media to provoke someone to speak up. Voice recorder application gave by the facilitator to the participant. participant choose a picture (comic figure) that they want to describe.

ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

After finished the implementation of voice recorder application to develop students speaking skill, the writer would report about students speaking score, scoring has standardized by (Brown). Base on the result of students speaking score, the school standardized English score was 73 to pass the lesson. The students consist of 35 students, Then, score consist of minimum score till maximum score, they are;

Table 1 score categories

Score categories	
90-100	Excellent
80-89	Very Good
70-79	Good
60-69	Enough
40-59	Weak
20-49	Very Poor

Before knowing the observation result the writer would be explain about the standard scoring speaking, Based on the data of students speaking score, which involving five aspect os speech they are grammar, vocabulary, fluency, pronunciation. The standard score was agree with Brown (2001) and every aspects has standard score one till five. Here was the students score base on teacher implementation using comic figure.

Table 2

SOLOM Teacher Observation Student Oral Language Observation Matrix					
Student's Name:			Grade:	Date:	
Language Observed			Administered By(signahure)		
		2	3		5
A.Comprehent ion	Canaat be sald to sederstand evan vinpic conversition.	Haw grout dificulty following what is seid. Can conprehtnd enly social conversation spoken slowly and with freqent repetitcns	Understande mest of uhat is said of slower-than-normal speed with repetitions	Understands nesely avereverything at notmal speech.Althou gh occasional repetitcns may be necenary	Unde tanin everyday conversation and normal classroom discustions
B.Fluency	English Speech uo balting and fragmartary as to make conversation vituality Inposabie	Usually hestan: oftcn foreed Into silence by langiage limitations	Speec in everyday cnversation and classroom discussion frequently dorupted by the mtadent's search foe the correct wanner of expression	Speech in everyday converiation and cdiassoot dscusions gencally flumt. with accasional lapseswhile the itident soches for the correct marnner of expresgicn	Speech in everyday conversation and classroom discusions fluent and effartess acprosimatin g that of anative speaker
C.Vocabelary	Vecablary Emhation 日和 extreme as te make conversstians vitually Iportibe	Misase of werds and vary limited comspechensi on quile difficult	Student frequently sses wring words cmversation somewhat limited because of inadequate vocabulary.	Student occasionally uases Exppropriate tare and/or mas repltrase iteas brecaaste of lesical mnadectacies	Use of vecabulary and idions approxisnale that of a native spraker
D.Promunciati on	Proeus:ciacio n prcbleae so severeas to make speoch wioially animelligible	Very haed ts undastied becaunte of proreetciatio n problems Mast frequently rpeat in order to make himberitati underdtood	Prominciatio peoblass necesadtate concentration aa Beart of the livener aod eccasionally leadto miuinderdtan dng	Always imelligible although the limener is consciens of a definite accent and eccasions insppropriate inkration paite 现A	Preeunciatio n and infreation sppreximale that of a native speaker
E.Grammar	Eimors in grammar and word ancer se severe asto	Grammar and ward meder emars make compeehenti on difficult	Makes freqant erers ef grummar and word order	Oocasicrally nades grunmaticsl and/or word order carons	Gratanar and waed order approximate that of a nadive

	make wech vinnually aniutdligible	Mast often mpbrest and/or matric him/hervelf to basie pallers	that occasionally obscure meaaing	that de nox: obecare menting	speaker
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Post-test

Table 3 Cumulative score cycle II

No	Score (xi)	Frequency (fi)	fi.Xi	Frequency Relative (f%)
1.	80	5	400	5 - x100 = 14% 35
2.	84	12	1008	12 -x100 = 34% 35
3.	88	13	1144	13 -x100 = 37% 35
4	92	3	276	3 — X 100 = 9% 35
5	96	2	192	2 —x100 = 6% 35
6	Σ	35	3020	100%

1. The students who got score 80 were 14% they were Diana Nopita, Nurcahyanti, Roby,sartiman,warnengsih.
2. Students who got score 84 were 34%. It include very good category.They were Aal Fauziah,Abdul Muis,Dian Ayu Lestari,Eki Yolani Putri,Elisia,Frizky Yustisio,Gilang,Haerudin ,Nunung Nuriah,Rani Sagibah,Sesa Sabita,Wawan.
3. The third part, students who got score 88 were 37%. They were Aldi Ardianto,Anang Permadi, Dion,Fidiah Ayu R, Indah Lestari, Kattah, Maryanto , Mohamad Johan,Novita wulan S,Sukesih,Tardiyana,Winda Silpiyani,Yogi Suwarno.
4. The second part, students who got score 92 were 9% it mean the students got excellent. They are: Aris hidayat, The second is M. Noris ,The last was Yeni,
5. The fifth part, students who got score 96 were 6% or two students who got excellent score category. They were Mega and Rizma risky, who last cyclegot score 64 for mega and 80 for Rizma risky.

Observation Form Toward English Speaking

Foreign Language Interaction Abalysis (FLINT)Moskowitz (1971)

No	Participants	Observation					Details
		1	2	3	4	5	

1	Aal Fauziah	3	2	3	2	3	<p>1. Interested in following instructional processes using comic figures.</p> <p>2. Able of asking and answering about the media from the teacher.</p> <p>3. Able to implementing the technique to develop students speaking skill through describing comic figures and feeling considering accuracy, fluency, vocabulary, grammar, and style.</p> <p>4. Able of convey information based on what the student have listened about the media.</p>
2	Abdul Muis	3	2	3	3	3	
3	Aldi Ardianto	2	3	3	3	2	
4	Anang Permadi	3	2	3	2	2	
5	Aris Hidayat	3	2	3	2	3	
6	Dian Ay u Lestari	2	2	3	3	3	
7	Diana Nopita	2	2	3	3	3	
8	Dion	3	2	3	3	3	
9	Eki Yolani Putri	3	2	3	3	3	
10	Elisia	3	2	3	2	2	
11	Fidiah Ayu R	3	1	3	3	3	
12	Frizky Yustisio	2	2	3	3	3	
13	Gilang	2	1	1	2	2	
14	Haerudin	2	1	2	2	2	
15	Indah Lestari	3	2	3	3	2	
16	Kattah	3	3	3	3	2	
17	M.Noris	3	3	3	3	2	
18	Maryanto	3	3	3	3	3	
19	Mega	3	3	3	3	3	
20	Mohamad	3	3	3	3	3	
	Johan						
21	Novita Wulan S	3	2	2	2	2	

22	Nunung Nuriah	3	2	2	3	3
23	Nur Cahyati	2	3	3	2	3
24	Rani Sagibah	3	3	2	3	3
25	Risma Rizky	3	3	3	3	2
26	Roby	3	2	2	3	3
27	Sartiman	3	3	3	3	2
28	Sesa Sabita	3	3	3	3	3
29	Suksesih	3	2	3	3	2
30	Tardiyana	3	2	3	2	3
31	Warnengsih	3	2	3	2	2
32	Wawan	3	2	1	3	3
33	Winda Silpiyani	3	3	3	3	2
34	Yeni	3	2	3	3	2
35	Yogi Suwarno	3	3	3	3	3
	Σ Score 1	27	13	28	25	21
	Σ Score 2	8	19	5	10	14
	Σ Score 1	0	3	2	0	0

Observation Score Feature:

A=3 B=2 C=1

A=VeryGood B=Good C=Fair

Observation Detail	1	2	3	4	5
A = <i>VeryGood</i>	77%	37%	80%	71%	60%
B = <i>Good</i>	23%	54%	14%	29%	40%
C = <i>Fair</i>	0%	9%	6%	0%	0%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Very Good Category

Based on the description of foreign language interaction analysis at point 1 there 77%students are interested to follow the intructional process. The second point were 37% student able of asking and answering about the media from the teacher. Third point were 80%,or stuentns Able to implementing the techique to develop students speaking skill trough descrbing comic figures and feeling considering accuracy, fluency, vocabulary, grammar,almost 100%.Fourth were 71% the students Able of confeving information based on what the student have listened about the media. The last category very good was 60% ,studets were able to expres their formation trough speech base on their favorite comic figures.

In good category the students in point 1 got 23% which interested to jin the lesson. In point 2were 54%,students able of asking and answering about the media from the teacher. In point 3 students were 14%

only few students which did not able to implementing the technique to develop students speaking skill through describing comic figures and feeling considering accuracy, fluency, vocabulary, grammar, and style. In point 4 were 29% in competence able of conveying information based on what the student have listened about the media, it indicated that students did hear the information effectively. In five category students were getting 40% in 5 Able to express their information through speech based on their favorite comic figures.

Fair Category

In fair category students there in 0% point 1, it means students interested to join the lesson. The second was 9%, indicated that only few students who passive. The third were 6% it means only two students who did able to implement the generic structure in cycle II. Fourth were 0% it means indicated that every students have better information toward their favorite comic figure. The fifth was 0% it means almost students able express their own language using comic figures.

CONCLUSION

The writer gives the implication and conclusion of the research, the writer also made suggestions for English teaching process for next research. The conclusions of the result are the following: Based on data analysis, the writer has gotten some conclusion, first. The use of comic figures as media able to developed students' speaking skill. Not only descriptive form as the main study but also comic figures encourage other language aspect to the students to be developed in their task preference. The last, student' response toward comic figures as media to develop students speaking skill was satisfied. The students are able to accept the media and enjoy it well.

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